

Microwave-assisted sequential extraction of fly ash : Studies on chemical speciation of zinc, copper, arsenic and manganese

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Coal fly ash due to its light weight and better mobility, is a significant solid pollutant. A sequential extraction procedure has been applied to determine the environmental mobility of zinc, copper, arsenic and manganese in fly ash. The original procedure of Tessier *et al.* has been modified using the microwave-assisted technique. The results obtained by summation of extractable amounts of copper, arsenic and manganese obtained in each step by the microwave procedure range from 88 to 99% of the total content, by microwave-assisted method, as compared to the standard non-certified value of NIST fly ash. For zinc, however, we obtain 117% of the metal content, by microwave-assisted method, as compared to the standard non-certified value of NIST fly ash. The elemental analyses of the individual leachates have been done by flame atomic absorption spectrometry and hydride generation atomic absorption spectroscopy. A drastic reduction in time viz. from 68 h in the original Tessier to <3.5 h in the microwave-assisted method has been obtained.

Determination of trace elements in fly ash samples has always been an interesting area of environmental research. Multielemental determination has been done, and about 58 elements have been determined¹. The transformation of these trace element species to environmentally mobile forms, include a vast range of competing reactions, complexations with organic/inorganic ligands, changes with oxidation state, precipitation, dissolution, ion exchange and metal particulate association².

In the study and control of toxic effects of trace elements, it has already been established that there is little significance of analysing the total amount of an element in environmental samples. This is because of significant differences in the toxic actions of different species of an element³. Hence the quantification of the chemical forms of the elements in fly ash is essential, in order to determine its mobility and bioavailability in the environment. Trace metal speciation refers to our ability to identify which form(s) of a given element or organometallic compound appear in a particular sample, and at what precise quantitative levels such chemicals occur⁴. Natural and anthropogenic environmental changes strongly influence the behaviour of trace elements.

Several sequential extraction procedures including those of Tessier *et al.*⁵ and its modifications⁶ have been extensively applied to aquatic sediments⁷, soils⁸, sewage sludges⁹ etc. In the Tessier scheme, the elements could be charac-

terized in the following fractions : exchangeable, carbonate bound, iron/manganese oxide bound, organic matter bound and residual fractions. The Tessier protocol later modified by several workers, has been applied to fly ash by using the classical technique, where each stage of the extraction scheme involved long hours of shaking in order to ensure maximum leaching. In the present work the extraction scheme has been modified, using microwave energy, for the acceleration of the sequential extraction of fly ash.

In this work, quantitative extraction has been applied to separate the binding forms of four trace elements (copper, manganese, arsenic and zinc), in the certified reference coal fly ash standard (NBS SRM 1633 b). The instrumental parameters i.e. power (wattage) and time of operation has been suitably adjusted to get the best results. The experimental data of conventional and microwave extraction schemes have been compared.

Flame atomic absorption spectrometry (FAAS) has been used to determine the elements like copper, manganese and zinc, while hydride generation atomic absorption spectrometry (HGAAS) has been applied for arsenic. The developed method has been applied to monitor the environmental mobilities of these elements in real fly ash specimens, collected from different thermal power plants, in close proximity to each other, in the industrial belt of Durgapur, West Bengal (India).

Results and discussion

Optimization of time of microwave irradiation :

From Fig. 1, it may be observed, that for the exchangeable species, extractions of copper and zinc require a time of 35 (5 × 7) min to give the maximum recovery, where recovery % may be defined as [(species extracted by microwave-assisted treatment)/species extracted by classical method] × 100. For manganese, maximum leaching is observed in 35 (5 × 7) min for exchangeables (Fig. 1), 40 (5 × 8) min is required for carbonate bound, 30 (5 × 6) min for iron/manganese oxide bound and 25 (5 × 5) min organically bound species. However, for arsenic leaching in the exchangeable and carbonate bound phases, the time periods taken are 35 (5 × 7) and 54 (6 × 9) min respectively. For leaching of copper, zinc and manganese it is seen that after a certain irradiation time (35 to 54 min) there is decrease in concentration of the respective element. This may be attributed to the reversible adsorption of metal ions in the remaining residue, due to prolonged microwave irradiation time. In the organically bound species a shorter time period (5 × 7 = 35min) has been required during ammonium acetate treatment, (after treatment with H₂O₂, as indicated in Scheme 1), for all the four elements.

Fig. 1. Optimization of microwave irradiation time of exchangeable species : (▼) Mn, (●) Zn, (▲) As, (■) Cu.

Optimization of microwave power :

The general trends for copper, zinc and arsenic have shown that a power of 180 watt gives the best recovery for the exchangeable (6 × 9 = 54 min), carbonate bound (5 × 9 = 45 min) and iron/manganese oxide bound (5 × 9 = 45 min) stages. For organo-species bound and residual species 5 × 7 = 35 and 5+5+4 = 14 min are necessary with 300 and 450 watts. However, for manganese, in case of carbonate

Scheme 1. Extraction flow-chart using classical and microwave assisted methods.

bound species, a power of 300 watt gives best recovery. In the organically bound state, the best recovery is obtained with a power of 300 watt for copper, zinc and manganese. In the case of arsenic, 180 watt still gives the best results. Above findings are with standard fly ash NBS SRM 1633 b.

Comparison of the results obtained from classical and microwave assisted extraction schemes :

The salient features of the results obtained from classical and microwave assisted techniques have been illustrated in Table 1.

The recovery percentages of manganese by microwave

Table 1. Extraction percentage of various elements by microwave assisted and classical techniques

Element	Certified value (µg/g) ^a	Classical method (µg/g) ^b	Microwave assisted method (µg/g) ^b
Cu	112.8 ± 2.6	88.1 ± 3.2	99.6 ± 2.4
Zn	210 (non certified)	258.7 ± 6.6	246.5 ± 4.5
Mn	131.8 ± 1.7	119.2 ± 2.3	118.9 ± 1.8
As	136.2 ± 2.6	126.1 ± 4.4	135.7 ± 3.1

^aNBS SRM 1633 b fly ash. ^bAverage of 5 determinations

Table 2. Results of sequential extraction of the different fly ash samples

Sample	Element	Exchangeable ($\mu\text{g/g}$) ^a	Carbonate bound ($\mu\text{g/g}$) ^a	Fe/Mn oxide bound ($\mu\text{g/g}$) ^a	Organically bound ($\mu\text{g/g}$) ^a	Residual ($\mu\text{g/g}$) ^a
1	Cu	8.8 ± 0.7	10.2 ± 0.3	8.9 ± 0.5	17.6 ± 0.7	40.1 ± 1.6
	Zn	8.5 ± 0.6	4.2 ± 0.3	3.7 ± 0.1	7.6 ± 0.5	14.3 ± 0.7
	As	9.1 ± 0.5	10.5 ± 0.5	8.7 ± 0.3	10.8 ± 0.4	3.5 ± 0.1
	Mn	19.2 ± 1.4	21.1 ± 0.7	12.1 ± 0.4	33.1 ± 0.4	3.4 ± 0.1
2	Cu	8.7 ± 0.3	10.6 ± 0.4	19.5 ± 0.8	11.4 ± 0.4	5.1 ± 0.2
	Zn	17.1 ± 0.5	10.1 ± 0.4	10.6 ± 0.8	12.1 ± 0.6	2.7 ± 0.1
	As	7.3 ± 0.4	3.6 ± 0.1	4.5 ± 0.1	5.5 ± 0.2	8.2 ± 0.4
	Mn	12.7 ± 0.4	21.7 ± 0.3	12.9 ± 0.3	7.1 ± 0.3	70.6 ± 0.6
3	Cu	8.1 ± 0.2	14.6 ± 0.6	2.3 ± 0.1	2.6 ± 0.2	10.9 ± 0.7
	Zn	16.1 ± 0.4	10.2 ± 0.5	9.7 ± 0.1	7.6 ± 0.1	8.6 ± 0.1
	As	9.8 ± 0.5	8.3 ± 0.6	3.2 ± 0.2	4.5 ± 0.2	1.7 ± 0.3
	Mn	13.6 ± 0.3	6.9 ± 0.3	8.1 ± 0.4	6.4 ± 0.1	7.6 ± 0.1

^aAverage of 5 determinations

assisted and classical methods have been found to be in good agreement (90.46% in case of classical and 90.21% by microwave extraction). About 81% of the manganese has been found to be associated with the residual phase. Much smaller amounts are found to be present as exchangeable and carbonate bound species. The very low amount of exchangeable manganese species shows its low bio-availability. A considerable percentage of copper is found in the exchangeable fraction. The classical leaching shows a higher percentage of copper in the exchangeable phase, compared to the microwave leaching. A good amount of copper has been found to be distributed between oxide bound and organic phases. For zinc, the results obtained from both the microwave and classical methods of extractions show an increase in metal concentration, compared to the standard non-certified value (210 $\mu\text{g/g}$). A large fraction of zinc remains in the carbonate bound and oxide bound phases. An extraction efficiency of 92% by microwave assisted and classical methods has been shown for arsenic. The most striking feature is that, a large fraction of it is in exchangeable and carbonate bound phases (23% and 38% respectively) and a minor portion remains in the residual phase. This shows that compared to copper, zinc or manganese, the environmental mobility of arsenic species is much higher.

Statistical comparison of the results by means of *t*-test ($P = 0.95$), for each element and the total content allows us to assure that for 5 replicate measurements the agreement with the certified values for manganese, arsenic and copper

is quite good, ranging from 88 to 99%. For zinc, 17.3% higher value is obtained, compared to the non-certified value of NIST fly ash standard. This procedure has been repeated for blank experiments, and after analysis of such blanks, the possibility of contamination between reagents and materials have been ruled out.

From Table 1, it may be observed, that the total dissolution by the microwave assisted method, gives slightly higher values (difference is < 4%) for total element content, compared to the sequential extraction procedure. This may be attributed to experimental errors which add up in each of the 5 sequential extraction steps, in spite of taking all precautions. Regarding the precision of the proposed method, for $n = 5$, the average RSD values obtained are < 5%. Using the microwave-assisted extraction at the optimum conditions, the results of the analysis of 3 samples of fly ash are shown in Table 2. From these results, it is clearly observed, that manganese and arsenic species show a higher environmental mobility compared to copper and zinc.

Experimental

Apparatus and reagents

A domestic microwave oven (Samsung CE 2933), of 2450 MHz frequency magnetron, with a maximum power of 900 watt, was used as microwave energy source. PTFE reactors with 115 ml internal volume, 1 cm cell wall thickness and hermetic screw caps were used for sample digestion. Determination of elemental concentrations was done by using a GBC Avanta atomic absorption spectrometer.

Hollow cathode lamps were used as radiation sources, with resonance lines at 324.7, 213.9, 279.5 and 193.7 nm for copper, zinc, manganese and arsenic respectively. Lamp intensity and slit width were suitably adjusted, according to instrumental requirements. A Systronic 362 digital pH-meter was used for pH measurements. An ordinary mechanical shaker was used for prolonged shaking of the leachates at ambient temperature. All reagents used were of A.R. grade.

Fly ash samples were collected in plastic bags from electrostatic precipitators of three power plants, from the industrial belt of Durgapur, West Bengal, India. Samples were dried at 105°, powdered and used for experimentation.

For conventional process, 500 mg of fly ash was treated following the protocol of Tessier (Scheme 1). Continuous mechanical agitation (16 h) was carried out, by using a mechanical shaker. The supernatant solution was carefully separated from the underlying solid phase by centrifugation and analysed for each element by AAS. For microwave-assisted process about 200 mg of sample has been taken and treated as indicated in the Scheme. The effect of microwave power on leaching was monitored, by increasing from 180 watt to 450 watt, the time was increased from 9 min to 63 min at regular intervals of 4–5 min for a particular leachate. A power higher than 450 watt was avoided in order to prevent dissociation of the metal complexes due to excessive heating or partial leaching from the next phase. Temperature was controlled within 70°. The corresponding leachate for a particular time interval, was subjected to AAS determination.

Conclusion :

The scheme of Tessier *et al.* was originally applied to sediment samples. In our work the method has been applied to different fly ash samples in order to assess the mobility and bioavailability of different elements using the rapid microwave-assisted extraction technique. While replacing the traditional method by microwave assisted method the time of treatment has been reduced from hours to minutes. Apart from significant shortening of time of operation, this process reduces the risk of contamination and involves a clean process technology. For manganese and arsenic, the use of microwave-assisted Tessier method

provides similar results in comparison to the traditional method. In case of copper and zinc, some differences have been found, however on the whole, both the methods provide similar informations regarding speciation of elements. The leachability of the analysed elements were different in the various samples of fly ash. Obviously, different distribution patterns have been observed. It is expected that this method can be successfully applied to fly ash and other atmospheric particulate samples, in order to gather information about the environmental mobility of more elements.

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